

Glycaemic Response to Intraoperative Dexamethasone in Non-Diabetic Patients Undergoing Brain Tumor Surgery

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Abstract

Background: Craniotomy for brain tumour resection is carried out frequently in neurosurgical practice. Intra-operative dexamethasone at doses of ≥ 8 mg has been demonstrated to decrease tumour related oedema and vascular permeability. This, however may be associated with hyperglycemia which can exacerbate brain injury. The routine use of peri-operative steroids in this group of patients makes it prudent to establish the extent of hyperglycemia in order to prompt treatment when necessary.

Objective: To establish glycaemic response to intraoperative dexamethasone in non-diabetic patients undergoing surgery for brain tumor.

Methodology: This was a longitudinal observational study involving 62 patients undergoing brain tumor surgery in a tertiary hospital. Baseline blood glucose was taken at induction of general anaesthesia, before intra-operative dexamethasone administration. Subsequently, four one-hourly, followed by four four-hourly serial blood glucose measurements were taken up to the 20th hour.

Results: Majority 36 (58%) of the patients enrolled were female. The median (IQR) age and body mass index were 43(32, 52) years and 22.0(20.0, 23.9) kg/m^{-2} respectively. The median (IQR) blood glucose was 5.0(4.20, 6.07) $mmol/L$ at induction. Following a single dose of 8mg of dexamethasone, there was a steady increase in the median (IQR) blood sugar to a peak of 7.8 (6.90, 9.0) $mmol/L$ at the 4th hour (T4), with a downward trend thereafter. Additionally, the proportion of patients with fasting blood glucose above > 7.8 $mmol/L$, > 10.0 $mmol/L$ (insulin-therapy threshold) and 11.1 $mmol/L$ gradually increased to a peak of 53% by the 3rd hour (T3), 23% by the 8th hour (T5) and 13% by the 4th hour (T4) respectively.

Conclusion: Administration of 8mg of dexamethasone to non-diabetic patients undergoing brain tumor surgery is associated with a significant, albeit temporary, increase in blood glucose concentration. Therefore, we recommend routine monitoring of blood glucose levels for at least 16 hours following dexamethasone administration in these patients.

Keywords: Brain Tumor; Dexamethasone; Hyperglycaemia; Edema

1. Introduction

Brain tumours and the effect of surgery may lead to an increase in brain oedema and sub-

sequently intracranial pressure, leading to poor post-operative outcomes (Wan et al. 2023). Vasogenic oedema results from extravasation of fluid into the brain parenchyma due to blood

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Received: 01 February 2023, Accepted: 01 March 2023 and available online 05 May 2023

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7900090>

brain barrier incompetence, which is partly caused by tumor induced oxidative stress. The interruption is primarily due to loosening of the inter-endothelial tight junctions (Chavda et al. 2022).

Dexamethasone results in significant neurological resolution in brain tumour associated oedema. This has led to its extensive use in neuro-oncological surgery and anaesthesia. The presence of brain tumour leads to production VEGF and Scatter factor leading to defective astrocytes (MC et al. 2004). The therapeutic regimen involves a 4-8 mg of intravenous dexamethasone followed by 4mg every 4- 6 hours (Goldman et al. 2022).

Dexamethasone is a glucocorticoid with minimal mineralocorticoid effects (low index of salt and water retention). Other factors supporting its choice include low tendency to induce psychosis, and a longer half-life (Jessurun, Hulsbergen, Cho, et al. 2019). It reduces vasogenic oedema within 8 hours, not only at molecular, but also at radiological and clinical levels (Kim et al. 2008). Additionally, it has antiemetic and analgesic effects (Mitchell et al. 2022). Its use therefore may confer indirect neuroprotective effects by blunting the hemodynamic response to vomiting and pain.

The most common metabolic complication of dexamethasone is hyperglycaemia. Single doses of 8 mg dexamethasone in a non-diabetic patient significantly increases blood glucose concentration over a 4-hour period (Jessurun, Hulsbergen, Lamba, et al. 2022, Pin-on et al. 2018, Lukins and Manninen 2005). Stress hyperglycaemia as a result of a complex interplay between endogenous catecholamine, cytokines and activation of hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis results in excess cortisol secretion and induction of gluconeogenesis. This is exacerbated by exogenous catecholamines and dexamethasone. The attendant hyperglycaemia worsens oxidative stress pathways and induces neuroinflammation (Parthasarathy et al. 2022, Qi et al. 2022).

In hyperglycaemia, hexokinase becomes saturated and glucose metabolism is diverted into the polyol pathway through aldose reductase leading to sorbitol production in appreciable amounts. Sorbitol leads to intracellular fluid shift with resultant brain oedema and oxidative stress (Tomlinson and Gardiner 2008, Pang et al. 2020). Several studies have indicated that hyperglycaemia in neurosurgical patients is associated with adverse outcomes, such as neuronal damage, poor wound healing, prolonged hospi-

tal stay and higher mortality (Tomlinson and Gardiner 2008, McGirt et al. 2008).

The Society for Ambulatory Anaesthesia (SAMBA), The American Association of Clinical Endocrinologist (AAACE), American Diabetes Association (ADA) and The Joint British Diabetes Societies guidelines all recommend treatment for blood glucose levels above 10mmols /L in both non diabetic and diabetic patients with a target control level of 6-10mmol/L (Li and Cummins 2022, Nakamura et al. 2021, Roberts et al. 2018).

The objective of this study was to evaluate the effect of single dose dexamethasone (8mg) on perioperative glycaemic trends in steroid naive patients undergoing craniotomy for brain tumors.

2. Material & Methods

This was a longitudinal observational study. Following ethical approval by the Kenyatta National Hospital and University of Nairobi Ethics Review Committee (Ref. No.KNH-ERC/A/19), adult patients undergoing surgery for brain tumor were recruited using consecutive sampling approach. Following induction with fentanyl (2 mcgkg^{-1}), propofol (2 mgkg^{-1}) and relaxation with cisatracurium (0.2 mgkg^{-1}), anaesthesia was maintained with isoflurane (0.8 – 1.2%) in air and dexmedetomidine infusion at ($1\text{ mcgkg}^{-1}\text{hr}^{-1}$) for 10 minutes followed by $0.2\text{--}0.7\text{ mcgKg}^{-1}\text{hr}^{-1}$. Aseptic blood sampling by finger pricking was done. Baseline blood glucose concentration at time zero (T0) was obtained up on achievement of surgical anesthesia. After dexamethasone administration, serial blood glucose levels were measured initially after every hour for 4 readings (T1-T4), followed by four, four-hourly readings (T5-T8).

Data pre-processing and analysis was done using R version 4.2.1 (2022-06-23). A probability value ($p < 0.05$) was considered statistically significant.

3. Results

Out of 62 patients that were enrolled, 58% were female. Their median age and body mass index were 43 $IQR(32,52)$ years and $22.0\text{ }IQR(20.0,23.9)\text{ kgm}^{-2}$ respectively. Majority of the patients (68%) were of American Society Physiological Status class III. 59 (95%) of the surgical procedures were elective. Meningiomas were the commonest indication for surgery (39%), followed by low-grade gliomas

(34%). They were anaesthetised for a median duration of 307 (218, 349) minutes.

Table 1. Summary Statistics

Variable	N=62
Gender, n(%) ²	
Male	26(42%)
Female	36(58%)
Age (years) ¹	43(32,52)
Body Mass Index (kgm^{-2}) ¹	22.0 (20.0, 23.9)
ASA Physiological Status, n(%) ²	
I	1(2%)
II	16(26%)
III	42(68%)
IV	3(4%)
Diagnosis, n(%) ²	
Meningioma	24(39%)
Low-grade glioma	21(34%)
Glioblastoma	7(11%)
Caraniopharyngioma	3(5%)
Other	7(11%)
Procedures, n(%) ²	
Elective	59(95%)
Emergency	3(5%)
Duration of Anaesthesia (minutes) ¹	307(218,349)
Median (IQR) ¹	
Count (Percentage) ²	

The median baseline (T0) blood glucose was 5.0 *IQR*(4.20, 6.07) *mmol/L*. Following intravenous dexamethasone (8 mg), there was an upward trend in blood glucose with a peak of 7.8 *IQR*(6.9, 9.0) *mmol/L* at the 4th (T4) which lasted up to the 16th (T7) post induction hour. On further analysis, the proportion of patients

with fasting blood glucose above 7.8 *mmol/L*, 10.0 *mmol/L* (insulin therapy threshold) and 11.1 *mmol/L* gradually increased to a peak of 53% by the 3rd hour (T3), 23% by the 8th hour (T5) and 13% by the 4th hour (T4) respectively. This was followed by a steady decline in the said proportions.

Figure 1. Blood Sugar Trends

Figure 2. Proportion of Patients with Fasting Blood Sugar ≥ 7.8 mmol/L

Figure 3. Proportion of Patients with Fasting Blood Sugar ≥ 10.0 mmol/L

Figure 4. Proportion of Patients with Fasting Blood Sugar ≥ 11.1 mmol/L

4. Discussion

In this study, institutional preoperative starvation protocol for anaesthesia was applied uniformly to elective patients, which comprised 95% of the study sample. After a minimum fasting period of 6 hours, the median baseline glucose was 5.0 mmol/L. 66% of the participants had a fasting blood glucose ≤ 5.6 mmol/L. A study involving > 1800 patients scheduled for coronary artery bypass surgery had 60% of its participants with fasting blood sugar ≤ 5.6 mmol/L (Anderson et al. 2005). Similarly, the periopera-

tive administration of dexamethasone and blood glucose concentrations in elective non-cardiac surgery trial revealed a median baseline glucose of 5.3 mmol/L in the non-diabetic arm (Corcoran et al. 2021). Following the administration of 8 mg of dexamethasone, there was a steady increase in the median blood glucose levels. A median increase in blood glucose from the baseline by 2.5 mmol/L was noted by the third hour. Nearly similar trends were demonstrated in other studies, where such a change in blood glucose occurred by the second intra-operative

hour (Lukins and Manninen 2005, Herbst et al. 2020, Polderman et al. 2018) .

Peak blood glucose levels were attained between the 4th (T4) and 16th (T7) hours, after which there was a decline. Similar patterns of transient hyperglycemia after a single dose of dexamethasone have been demonstrated in other studies, with peak plasma glucose by the eighth hour (Lukins and Manninen 2005). 88% of the study subjects had an increase of more ≥ 2.3 *mmol/L* from the baseline. Previous studies have demonstrated that this magnitude of increase may be enough to result in neuronal injury and death (Liu-DeRyke et al. 2009). It is worth noting that 88.7% of patients achieved blood glucose levels above 7.8 *mmol/L* which is the treatment threshold for fasting blood glucose. Additionally, 30% had blood glucose levels ≥ 11.1 *mmol/L* at some point during the study. In a Cochrane review, even a slight increase in blood glucose resulting from dexamethasone ad-

ministration was established to be an independent predictor for insulin therapy among non-diabetic patients (Sethi et al. 2016).

43% of the participants achieved blood glucose of > 10.0 *mmol/L* at some point during the study. The international guidelines for management of diabetes recommend the initiation of insulin therapy to a target blood sugar of ≤ 10 *mmol/L*.

5. Conclusion

Administration of 8mg of dexamethasone to non-diabetic patients undergoing brain tumor surgery is associated with a significant, albeit temporary, increase in blood glucose concentration. Therefore, we recommend routine monitoring of blood glucose levels for at least 16 hours following dexamethasone administration in these patients

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